

DOMINIK ZIĘCINA¹ ,
SEBASTIAN SALATA¹

Corrigendum: A taxonomic revision of the *Temnothorax kemali* species-group (Hymenoptera: Formicidae)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17474262>

¹ Myrmecological Laboratory, Department of Biodiversity and Evolutionary Taxonomy,
University of Wrocław, Poland,

² Department of Biology, Faculty of Sciences, Trakya University, Edirne, Türkiye
DZ: e-mail: dominik.ziecina@uwr.edu.pl, ORCID: 0000-0002-8951-9102
LB: e-mail: lech.borowiec@uwr.edu.pl, ORCID: 0000-0001-5668-6855
SS: e-mail: sebastian.salata@uwr.edu.pl, ORCID: 0000-0003-0811-2309
KK: e-mail: kadrikiran@trakya.edu.tr, ORCID: 0000-0001-7983-0194
CK: e-mail: celalkaraman@trakya.edu.tr, ORCID: 0000-0002-2158-5592

We recently published the description of a new ant species *Temnothorax guzel* (ZIĘCINA *et al.* 2025). However, the depository of the holotype was omitted by error. Therefore, according to the current International Code of Zoological Nomenclature, the new species name would be a nomen nudum and unavailable (ICZN 1999: Art. 16.4.2). In this corrigendum, we indicate the holotype and paratypes depository, which we did not include in the original paper.

***Temnothorax guzel* ZIĘCINA, KIRAN, KARAMAN, BOROWIEC & SALATA sp. nov.**

Temnothorax guzel ZIĘCINA *et al.*, 2025: 772, figs. 1–8.

Primary type information:

Primary type material: holotype worker.

Primary type locality: Türkiye: Kütahya, Simav, Efir Vill., 39.2151/28.79281, 1170 m, 07/2449a, 6.IX.2007 (C. Karaman).

Primary type depository: Entomological Museum of Trakya University (EMTU), Edirne, Türkiye.

Secondary type information:

Secondary type material: 4 paratype workers.

Secondary type locality: same as for holotype.

Secondary type depository: Museum of Natural History, University of Wrocław (MNH), Wrocław, Poland.

REFERENCES

ZIĘCINA D., KIRAN K., KARAMAN C., BOROWIEC L., SALATA S. 2025. A taxonomic revision of the *Temnothorax kemali* species-group (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Annales Zoologici* (Warsaw) 75 (3):769-782. DOI: 10.3161/00034541ANZ2025.75.3.007.

Accepted: 20 October 2025; published: 29 October 2025

Licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution License <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>